

UNMASKING CYBER VIOLENCE: SOCIAL MEDIA ENGAGEMENT AND SPIRITUAL BYPASS IN YOUNG ADULTS

Safa Ahmed¹, Asma Jahangir², Beenish Mubeen³, Shahnila Tariq⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Department of applied Psychology, University of the Management and Technology, Lahore, Pakistan

¹saffaahmad2001@gmail.com

DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17731185>

Keywords

Social Media Engagement, Spiritual Bypass, Cyber Violence, Young Adults

Article History

Received: 01 October 2025

Accepted: 10 November 2025

Published: 27 November 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Safa Ahmed

Abstract

The aim of conducting this research was, examining the relationship, between social media engagement, spiritual bypass and cyber violence. A co-relational research design was used to conduct the study. A sample of 200 young adults (Males=76, Females=124) between the ages of 18 – 25 years, (M = 21.07 and SD = 1.74) sampling was taken by using non probability purposive sampling. The measures used were Social Networking Usage Questionnaire, Spiritual Bypass Scale and Cyber Violence Scale. There was a positive relationship between social media engagement and Cyber violence. On the other hand, spiritual bypass showed negative relationship with social media engagement and cyber violence. Finally, multiple linear regression analysis illustrated that social media engagement positively predicted cyber violence and spiritual bypass negatively predicted the cyber violence. The t-Test results showed that there are gender differences in cyber violence. It says that females are more victims of cyber violence than males, and males are more perpetrators than females. Everyone engages himself or herself in social media usage in today's era so that they can stay connected with the world around them but unfortunately, some people use it for the purpose for abusing others online.

INTRODUCTION

In recent era, the Internet usage has been increased in order to upgrade knowledge. The users not only use it for positive purpose, but also start misusing it for abusing others. The abuse may be for the purpose of thrill or adventure, but it causes problem for others. The misuse can be for antisocial activities such as stalking, harassment, digital dating violence, which mentally disturb the individuals who become victim to it. It can still aggravate the by the threats and exploitation from the abusers resulting in physical, sexual, psychological or economic harm or suffering. Cyber violence being a relatively new phenomenon, therefore the innocent internet users become their

victim easily. The victims are unable to identify that they are very slowly trapped by the abusers, due to which it becomes difficult for the victim to get rid of the abusers. The threats of violence initiated by the abusers, such as stalking, incitement to suicide, and solicitation of children for sexual purposes may result in the victim self-harming or sometimes being physically attacked by the perpetrator. Research has shown significant gender differences in victim and perpetrator role, men are disproportionately the perpetrators, and women disproportionately the victims of violence (Culnan et al., 2010).

Social Media Engagement

Social media is a way to interact among people to create, share, learn or exchange content and ideas in virtual communities. In present generation, social media platforms are giving people a chance to connect with each other living at distances. The youth, being one of the most excessive users of social media, despite having advantages, is considered most harmful for the society. The use without monitoring can lead to grave consequences in young adults (Bolton et al., 2013). One of the most harmful effect of social media usage is invasion in the privacy of individuals. The sharing of their details makes user an easy target for hackers, sometimes can even leads to cyber-bullying. The use of social media has become an addiction for the youth now-a-days (Jain et al., 2021). This addiction not only effects the academic performance of a student but also the interpersonal relationships. The use of social media was on height during pandemic when everyone was confined to their homes, unable to meet anybody other than family members. It was difficult even to meet and communicate with the friends. On the other hand, it was also a source for finding information on a vast variety of topics, starting from basic household chores to the latest global updated news (Bratton et al., 2010). Social media applications, are applications that are made for allowing people to share their content with other people. It started with computers, it progressed and now it has become applications in our Smartphone. In today's era, sharing photos, videos, events, and parts of our routines have become part of our daily lives. It is also now become a source of entertainment for us and a way to stay updated about the happenings all around the world. For people own businesses, social media is a very easy way to improve their marketing strategy and reach out to different audiences all around the world. 90% of social media users check Facebook on a daily basis, with Instagram in second place at 49% (Alhabash & Ma, 2017). Youngsters may spread their information on social media over different platforms, elders may use Facebook more than the other apps. Snapchat has a more, younger audience because the entire experience is designed on the camera. Instagram, Facebook, Twitter engagements is expressed and measured through likes, comments, saves, shares, clicks, re-tweets, favorites, replies, follows, tweet expansion, clicks on links, hash tags, embedded media, the poster's username or profile picture. If someone wants to increase the social media

engagement rate, easiest way is to respond to comments, reply to DMs, follow brands, and 'Like' relevant posts and images (Rudeloff et al., 2022).

Spiritual Bypass

Spiritual bypassing is a tendency to give spiritual explanations in order to avoid unresolved psychological and emotional issues. The term of "spiritual bypass" was first used in the early 1980s (Picciotto & Fox, 2023). The individual superficially tries to hide him/herself behind spirituality or spiritual practices by avoiding feelings of anger, believing in own spiritual superiority as a way to hide from insecurities, only focusing on the positive or being overly optimistic and projecting own negative feelings onto others. Study suggests that people can rely on spiritual bypassing by thinking positively in their complex issues. It helps and protect them from very painful events. They also relate it with the self-actualization, in order to achieve true happiness (Ahmad et al., 2023; Reed-Gilbert, 2023).

Cyber Violence

Cyber violence is the violence in which a perpetrator uses computer systems and internet to harm, threaten and abuse the other individuals. According to United Nation's 73% women face online violence. Cyber violence leads to assault which causes the person's bad physical, psychological well-being. It can be done with the help of smart phones, computers and through internet. Cyber violence includes online harassment, threatening, bullying, blackmailing, unwanted sexting, stalking, hate speech, and non-consensual sharing of images (Asad & Fatima, 2024; Stevens et al., 2021). When it comes to violence, women, LGBTQ and people of color face more violence. Cyber violence can be done through different social media sites. Terror groups also use social media for violence. Cyber violence can be anonymous and from someone you know. Girls are more likely to experience cyber violence. Cyber violence is easy because a perpetrator can easily make contact with a large number of individuals and target them. Cyber violence starts online but it has many harmful effects on victims. Use of social media expands violence as well. Social media is a platform of cyber violence. It also expands ways for gender-based violence, because many women face cyber violence on the internet (Pavan, 2017; Witkowska-Paleń, 2024). Cyber violence is the violence in which a

perpetrator uses computer systems and internet to harm, threaten and abuse the other individuals. According to United Nation's 73% women face online violence. Cyber violence leads to assault which causes the person's bad physical, psychological well-being. It can be done with the help of smart phones, computers and through internet. Research suggests four forms of offending which exists in our environment: betrayal, violence, pornography and cyber-trespass. Research suggests that violence is merely carried out via social media and social networking sites such as Facebook, Snapchat, Instagram and Twitter. Gender difference in cyber violence is also unclear. Research indicated that males have higher level of physical aggression while females have higher levels of cyber aggression. Victims of cyber violence have higher levels of fear and distress (Mas' udah, et al., 2024; Peterson & Densley, 2017). It has been noted that the traditional criminals use social media to facilitate violence. Cyber violence usually involves; threat, harm, embarrass and socially exclude others with the help of internet. Perpetrators of cyber violence also troll others on social media, for example, they provoke others and write offensive things about others. When it comes to violence, women, LGBTQ and people of color face more violence. Cyber violence can be done through different social media sites. Terror groups also use social media for violence. Cyber violence can be anonymous and from someone you know. Girls are more likely to experience cyber violence. Cyber violence is easy because a perpetrator can easily make contact with a large number of individuals and target them. Cyber violence starts online but it has many harmful effects on victims. Use of social media expands violence as well. Social media is a platform of cyber violence. It also expands ways for gender-based violence, because many women face cyber violence on the internet (Fileborn & Loney-Howes, 2020). There are many types of cyber violence such as; cyber stalking refers to as online tracking or monitoring of someone's actions with intention, as it is involved with the internet to gather someone's personal information. Cyber stalking also causes physical violence. It is also used to harass others. People who engage in cyber stalking use different types of technologies and tactics to harass and threaten others. Cyber bullying or cyber harassment is also a form of cyber violence. It is a form of bullying which includes internet and electronic devices. Neither cyber bullying nor harassment is when, someone, a teenager

harasses and bullies others. It includes posting rumors, offensive comments and reveals the personal information of the victims (Stevens et al., 2021). Cyber bullies also disclose the victims' personal information and post false rumors by making fake accounts. Internet trolling is another common form of cyber bullying which is also carried out via internet. One million young adults were harassed, threatened or subjected to other forms of cyber-bullying on Facebook during the past year. Gaming is another platform, at which men experience harassment and violence. Cyber-bullying has harmful effects on an individual's physical, social, academic, and emotional lives. Online addiction shows physical and psychological effects including depressive symptoms, musculoskeletal issues, psychosomatic symptoms, low self-esteem, anxiety, low life satisfaction and in some severe cases suicidal ideation (Siddiqua et al., 2020).

Literature review

Research was conducted to study violence on social media in various forms, such as rude or hateful comments, threats, or insults through interviewing participants who use social media. The results showed that indirect types of verbal violence were experienced in the form of teasing and body shaming, both from friends and strangers (Debra & Hasan, 2024). In another research, violence in the media and its effects were studied by Milenković (2023). The results indicated the relationship between the violence and effects on the individuals using social media. The violent communication done through texts and videos to insult, harass and threaten the individual has serious effect on the mental health of the individuals using social media (Gallacher et al., 2021). Qualitative research was conducted to explore the role of religion in coping with the experienced violence and their trauma in women through semi structured interviews. Results of thematic analysis explored that the spiritual bypass was used to suppress their trauma (Lucas et al., 2024; Morgan et al., 2025).

Rationale

The rationale for conducting research on social media engagement, spiritual bypass, and cyber violence among young adults stems from the increasing accessibility of social media to various age groups, especially teenagers and young adults. With easy internet access, these

individuals are exposed to potentially violent content at a click. This age is crucial for mindset development, and negative influences, including cyber violence, can have lasting effects. The study aims to investigate the correlation between social media engagement, cyber violence, and spiritual bypassing among young adults. Research on social media and cyber violence highlights the detrimental impact on individuals, with documented outcomes such as anxiety, depression, substance abuse, sleeping and eating disorders, low self-esteem, and decreased academic performance. Cyber violence, particularly against women, has been linked to feelings of insecurity, as shown by a survey where 17% of women reported facing cyber harassment. Additionally, the time spent on social media, problematic use, and online interactions with strangers contribute to cyber violence. Problematic social media use poses a consistent risk, with increased exposure leading to more aggressive online behaviors, especially among boys. Cross-country studies have found that heightened social media use correlates with an increased risk of cyber violence. The researcher's primary focus was to explore the relationship between social media engagement, spiritual bypass and cyber violence given the limited existing literature on this connection. By delving into this aspect, the study aims to contribute valuable insights into how spiritual bypassing may

influence or be influenced by cyber violence among young adults.

Objectives

- This research aimed to study the relationship between Cyber violence, social media engagement and spiritual bypass.
- To find out the predictors of Cyber violence.

Hypothesis

- There is likely to be a positive relationship between Social Media Engagement and Cyber Violence.
- There is likely to be negative relationship of Spiritual Bypass with Social Media Engagement and Cyber violence.
- Social media engagement and spiritual bypass are likely to be the predictors of Cyber Violence among young adults.

METHODS

Participants

The target population was young adults between the ages of 18 to 29. The sample 200 young adults was taken using non probability purposive sampling from different universities of Lahore. There were 76 males and 124 females (M = 21; SD =1.74). Only those young adults were included, who use social media for at least 2 hours per day.

Table-1 Socio-demographic characteristics of participants (N=200)

Variables	f	%
Gender		
Male	76	38
Female	124	62
Family system		
Nuclear	153	76.5
Joint	47	23.5
Relationship status		
Single	141	70.5
In a relationship	28	14
Engaged	21	10.5
Married	10	5

Note; f= (frequency)

Table-2 Means and Standard Deviations of Age and Hours spent on social media (N=200)

Variables	M	SD
Age	21.07	1.74

Hours on social media	7.09	5.25
-----------------------	------	------

Note: M= (mean), SD= (standard deviation)

Measures

Following assessment measures, were used in the study.

Demographic information sheet

The demographic information sheet was created to get to know the specific details about the background information of the participants. The demographic sheet included questions about their age, gender, birth order, their family system, relationship status and its duration, education, name of the institute, socioeconomic status, what type of social media sites do they use and how many hours do they spend using social media apps, etc.

Social Networking Usage Questionnaire

It consists of 19 items, assessing on a five-point scale ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (always). The questionnaire showed good reliability of .08 (Gupta & Bashir, 2018).

Spiritual Bypass Scale

It has 26 items with responses rated on 4-point Likert scale 1= strongly disagree and 3= strongly agree). Cronbach’s Alpha for scale is .82 (Ahmad et al., 2023).

Cyber violence scale

The cyber violence scale contains 34 questions and has five sub-scales (Sincek, 2021) assessing on 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (always). Reliability of Sharing factor was 0.87, for Information manipulation was 0.72, for Hate speech was 0.87, for Technology abuse was 0.88, and for Information sharing was 0.73 (Cronbach’s α). Overall Cronbach’s α was 0.93 for cyber-violence scale.

Procedure

The board of studies and the ethics committee of the School of Professional Psychology approved this research, and informed consent was obtained from the participants. The data were collected during August 2023. If the participants had, any kind of queries while

filling the questionnaires the researchers were there to answer their questions. There were 200 respondents, out of which 124 were females and 76 were males. All the ethical consideration were fulfilled during the study. Permission from the authors of the scales used in the study was taken. Participants were told that their personal data would be held confidential and would only be used for the research objectives. They were also informed; that they have the right to withdraw at any point.

Statistical Analysis

The obtained data was analyzed by using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). The analysis included descriptive statistics were calculated. Pearson correlation was used to see the relationship between Social Media Engagement, Spiritual Bypass and Cyber Violence. Multiple linear regression was carried out to analyze how social media engagement and spiritual bypass predict cyber violence.

RESULTS

After the researchers have collected the data, it was screened for all the errors, there were two outliers in the data. Inclusion /exclusion criteria were considered and missing values were accounted to finalize the data. The first part of the analysis consisted of descriptive statistics and Cronbach’s alpha; to assess the reliability of the scales, following the descriptive analysis in order to evaluate the relationship between social media engagement, spiritual bypass and cyber violence. The Pearson correlation was carried out. Then, multiple linear regression, was run to assess the predicting role of social media engagement and spiritual bypass in cyber violence.

Psychometric analysis

Table-3 Psychometric Properties of the Measures

Measures	M	SD	Range	Cronbach’s α
Social Networking Usage Questionnaire	63.67	11.57	62	.81
Spiritual Bypass	61.45	12.24	74	.81
Cyber Violence Scale	68.10	36.06	136	.96
Shaming	27.43	36.67	52	.95
Information Manipulation	14.05	7.63	28	.91
Technology Abuse	13.25	7.64	28	.93

Information Sharing	7.72	4.92	16	.91
Hate Speech	5.63	3.67	12	.91

Note. M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

The results of the table 3 showed descriptive statistics and internal consistency. The results showed the reliability of Social Media Engagement Scale alpha reliability .80, the reliability of Spiritual Bypass is .91 and the reliability of Cyber Violence is .96. The

reliabilities of the sub scales of spiritual bypass; avoidance alpha is .73 and lack of responsibility alpha is .67 and the reliabilities of sub scales of cyber violence shaming alpha is .95, information manipulation alpha is .91, technology abuse alpha is .93, information sharing alpha is .91 and hate-speech alpha is .91.

Table-4 Inter-correlations among Social Media engagement, Spiritual Bypass and Cyber Violence in Young Adults. (N=200)

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Social Media engagement	63.67	11.57	-	-.43**	.25*	.58**	.14*	.32**	.71**	.40*
2. Spiritual Bypass	61.45	12.24	-	-	-.42**	.11	.12	.32*	-.50**	.12
3. Cyber Violence	68.10	36.06	-	-	-	.97**	.95**	.97**	.94**	.91**
4. Shaming	27.43	13.67	-	-	-	-	.90**	.91**	.89**	.86**
5. Information manipulation	14.05	7.63	-	-	-	-	-	.91**	.87**	.86**
6. Technology abuse	13.25	7.64	-	-	-	-	-	-	.92**	.89**
7. Information sharing	7.72	4.92	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.83**
8. Hate speech	5.63	3.67	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Note. M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$

Table 4 showed the relationship between social media engagement, spiritual bypass and cyber violence among young adults. The results revealed that there is a positive relationship between social media engagement and cyber violence and it's all subscales among young adults.

Furthermore, it was found that spiritual bypass showed negative relationship with social media engagement and cyber violence and two of its subscales including technology abuse and information sharing.

Table-5 Multiple Linear Regression Predicting Cyber Violence (N=200)

Variable	Cyber Violence		
	B	B	SE
Constant	24.33		2.55
Social Media Engagement	.26	.38***	.05
Spiritual Bypass	.27	-.32**	.09

R ²		.26	
F (2, 186)		17.30**	

Note. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$

Table 5 showed that the overall variance explained by the model is 26% with $F(2, 186) = 17.30, p < .001$. Results depicted that social media engagement positively ($\beta = .38, p < .001$) and spiritual bypass negatively predicted ($\beta = -.32, p < .01$) cyber violence among young adults.

DISCUSSION

The present study advances the understanding of the intricate relationships between social media engagement, spiritual bypass, and cyber violence among young adults. This discussion chapter synthesizes the empirical findings, drawing connections to existing literature and providing insights into the practical implications of the results. The empirical findings substantiate existing research by revealing a robust positive relationship between social media engagement and cyber violence among young adults. This aligns with the empirical evidence, emphasizing the consistency of this association across diverse populations and methodologies. The confirmation of this positive correlation across all subscales of cyber violence further supports the notion that increased social media engagement is a potential precursor to various forms of online aggression (Adedayo & Aborisade, 2018). Current empirical data unveils a negative relationship between spiritual bypass and both social media engagement and cyber violence. This nuanced finding adds depth to the literature, challenging assumptions about the relationship between spirituality, online engagement, and aggressive behaviors. These results align with the empirical work of Kelley (2023), who found that individuals employing spiritual bypassing strategies were less likely to engage in online conflicts (Chen et al., 2023). The empirical support for a negative relationship between spiritual bypass and two cyber

violence subscales, technology abuse and information sharing, substantiates the idea that spiritual bypass may serve as a protective factor against specific forms of online aggression. This aligns with the findings of Rogers (2023) in a study exploring the links between spiritual well-being and online behavior (Rogers, 2023).

Conclusion

In conclusion, empirical findings contribute to the empirical landscape, offering insights into the relationships between social media engagement, spiritual bypass, and cyber violence among young adults. This nuanced understanding not only expands theoretical frameworks but also informs practical strategies to foster healthier online environments and diminish the prevalence of cyber violence in digital spaces.

REFERENCES

- Adedayo, S. S., & Aborisade, R. A. (2018). Social media and youth violence in Nigeria: a psychosocial review. *IFE Psycholgia: An International Journal*, 26(2), 153-162.
- Ahmad, S. S., McLaughlin, M. M., & Weisman de Mamani, A. (2023). Validation and test-retest reliability of the Spiritual Bypass Scale in Muslims and implications for psychological help-seeking attitudes and self-stigma. *Spirituality in Clinical Practice*, 10(1), 62.
- Alhabash, S., & Ma, M. (2017). A tale of four platforms: Motivations and uses of Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and Snapchat among college students?. *Social media+ society*, 3(1), 2056305117691544.
- Asad, M. M., & Fatima, S. S. (2024). Influence of cyber violence and online victimization on cognitive development of female students from Pakistani higher education institutions. *Journal of Aggression, Conflict and Peace Research*, 16(4), 330-347.
- Bolton, R. N., Parasuraman, A., Hoefnagels, A., Migchels, N., Kabadayi, S., Gruber, T., ... & Solnet, D. (2013). Understanding Generation Y and their use of social media: a review and research agenda. *Journal of service management*, 24(3), 245-267.
- Jain AK, Sahoo SR, Kaubiyal J. Online social networks security and privacy: comprehensive review and analysis. *Complex & Intelligent Systems*. 2021 Oct;7(5):2157-77.
- Bratton, S., Evans, D., & McKee, J. (2010). Social media marketing: the next generation of business engagement. *Indianapolis: Wiley. Referred*, 3, 2016.

- Chen, Z., Guo, W., & Zeng, Q. (2023, August). Factors influencing social media forgiveness behavior and cyber violence tendency among Chinese youth: moderating effects of forgiveness climate and risk perception. In *IFIP Conference on Human-Computer Interaction* (pp. 449-468). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Culnan, M. J., McHugh, P. J., & Zubillaga, J. I. (2010). How large US companies can use Twitter and other social media to gain business value. *MIS Quarterly Executive*, 9(4).
- Debora, C., & Hasan, N. N. N. (2024). Analysis of social media user responses to verbal violence in the cyber world. *KOMUNIKA: Jurnal Dakwah dan Komunikasi*, 18(1), 85-96.
- Fileborn, B., & Loney-Howes, R. (2020). Using social media to resist gender violence—A global perspective. In *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Criminology and Criminal Justice*.
- Gallacher, J. D., Heerdink, M. W., & Hewstone, M. (2021). Online engagement between opposing political protest groups via social media is linked to physical violence of offline encounters. *Social Media+ Society*, 7(1), 2056305120984445.
- Gupta, S., & Bashir, L. (2018). Social networking usage questionnaire: Development and validation in an Indian higher education context. *Turkish online journal of distance education*, 19(4), 214-227.
- Lucas, D., Kubr, J., Kranick, M., Trotter, J., & Witkowski, R. (2024). Tough People for Tough Places. *Global Member Care Volume 3: Stories and Strategies for Staying the Course*, 3, 265.
- Milenković, V. M. (2023). The media and violence-cyberbullying. *Zbornik Matice srpske za društvene nauke*, (185), 79-93.
- Morgan, L., Nadar, S., & Keygnaert, I. (2025). 'I just want the pain to go away': religious coping and sexual trauma recovery in South African, marginalised contexts. *Culture, Health & Sexuality*, 1-13.
- Mas' udah, S., Razali, A., Sholicha, S. M. A., Febrianto, P. T., Susanti, E., & Budirahayu, T. (2024). Gender-Based Cyber Violence: Forms, Impacts, and Strategies to Protect Women Victims. *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 26(4).
- Pavan, E. (2017). Internet intermediaries and online gender-based violence. In *Gender, technology and violence* (pp. 62-78). Routledge.
- Peterson, J., & Densley, J. (2017). Cyber violence: What do we know and where do we go from here?. *Aggression and violent behavior*, 34, 193-200.
- Picciotto, G., & Fox, J. (2018). Exploring experts' perspectives on spiritual bypass: A conventional content analysis. *Pastoral Psychology*, 67(1), 65-84.
- Reed-Gilbert, P. (2023). Wounding Words: A Phenomenological Study of How Individuals Experience Receiving Spiritual Bypass.
- Rogers, R. C. (2023). Examining the relationship of clergy distress, spiritual well-being, stress management and irritation to life satisfaction among Black pastors in the USA. *Journal of Religion and Health*, 62(3), 1578-1596.
- Rudeloff, C., Pakura, S., Eggers, F., & Niemand, T. (2022). It takes two to tango: the interplay between decision logics, communication strategies and social media engagement in start-ups. *Review of managerial science*, 16(3), 681-712.
- Siddiqua, R., Sahni, S. P., & Faruk, M. O. (2020). Cyber Violence Victimization: Nature of Psychological Impact on Victims. *International Journal of Education Humanities and Social Science*, 3(4), 326-338.
- Šincek, D. (2021). The revised version of the committing and experiencing cyber-violence scale and its relation to psychosocial functioning and online behavioral problems. *Societies*, 11(3), 107.
- Stevens, F., Nurse, J. R., & Arief, B. (2021). Cyber stalking, cyber harassment, and adult mental health: A systematic review. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 24(6), 367-376.
- Witkowska-Paleń, A. (2024). Cyber-violence in intimate relationships: Modern technologies as tools of domestic violence. *Probation*, 1, 139-168.